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A 3D-Printing Metasurface-Augmented Half-Circle Maxwell Fisheye Lens for Millimetre-Wave Analogue Beamforming

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Abstract. This article presents a 2D metasurface-augmented half-circle Maxwell fisheye lens (HMFL) designed to move its focal axis to a targeted direction with a maximum elevation angle of 45° , suitable for switchers and power division networks in the millimetre wave (mmWave) band. This metasurface-augmented beamformer enables consistent analogue performance across a bandwidth of 22 - 32 GHz. The proposed beamformer features a reflective metasurface consisting of 2×40 Phoenix unit cells and is integrated with a 10-dielectric zone HMFL in the diameter segment opposite the antenna source. A horn antenna feed is used for excitation in normal and oblique incidences of $\phi_i = -15^\circ$ and $\phi_i = -30^\circ$. The designed lens prototype was fabricated with 3D-printing technology and printed metasurfaces for several particular cases of focal displacement. The measurements of the proposed HMFL beamformer are presented, demonstrating a close correlation between simulated and experimental results.

Keywords: Metasurface, analogue beamformer, antenna, Maxwell fisheye lens, RF switch

1. Introduction

Inhomogeneous dielectric lenses, such as the Maxwell fisheye lens (MFL) [1], the Luneburg lens [2], the Eaton lens [3] and the Gutman lens [4], feature gradient refractive index (GRIN) characteristics that present unique and beneficial properties. These lenses are integral to various antenna systems to be used in applications such as imaging, switching, radar, beamsteering, beamforming and communication systems. These lens-based antenna systems are useful at millimetre-wave (mmWave) frequencies because of their practical size, even when they are multiple wavelengths large. Their notable advantages include broadband operation, low development complexity, precise focusing abilities, directive beams and the capacity to create multiple beams, all contributing to their performance.

Challenges such as achieving a precise refractive index distribution, while having multi-wavelength large physical dimensions have limited the practical implementation of the spherical MFL, particularly at lower frequencies [5, 6]. In response, researchers developed the half-circle Maxwell fisheye lens (HMFL) by adapting the principles of the Luneburg lens to enable a directed beam [7]. Although the Luneburg lens typically achieves higher directivity, it requires a double dielectric volume compared to the HMFL, which presents the HMFL as a more material-efficient alternative [8].

The MFL and HMFL have shown significant potential in various applications, including directive beams [9], beam splitters [10] and beamforming technologies [11]. Recently, advances in metamaterials and metasurfaces have provided new opportunities to augment these lenses. Specifically, integrating these materials with the HMFL led to enhancements in directive beam capabilities [12], multibeam functionality [13, 14] and power efficiency [15].

Recent progress in time-varying coding metasurfaces has improved the control and conversion of harmonics, which are important for wireless communication, radar sensing and biological monitoring [16, 17]. Metasurfaces can also steer beams in two dimensions [18], enable programmable beam steering [19] and increase the field of view [20].

In this article, we proposed a novel 2D metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer, using an array of Phoenix unit cells designed at 28 GHz.

The paper proposes a design methodology for the metasurface-augmented HMFL that enables displacement of a reflected focal point around the circumference of the lens. We demonstrate numerical and experimental verification of the methodology for several particular cases of the focal point position.

2. Methods

2.1. Maxwell Fisheye Lens

In this paper, we analyse a 2D MFL, which is characterised by an infinite extension along z , with its refractive index profile in the xy -plane mirroring that of the equatorial plane in a traditional MFL. This implies that the specific spatial coordinates within the xy -plane determine the refractive index distribution within the MFL. Consequently, this spatially variant refractive index plays a pivotal role in the quasi-optical properties of the lens. This variation is depicted in Figure 1 and is mathematically expressed as

$$n(r) = \sqrt{\epsilon_r} = \frac{n_o}{1 + \left(\frac{r}{R}\right)^2} \quad (1)$$

where ϵ_r represents the relative dielectric permittivity, n is the refractive index, and n_o is the refractive index at the centre of the lens. The radial distance r follows the condition $0 \leq r \leq R$.

Figure 1. Distribution of the relative dielectric permittivity and ray trajectories inside the 10 dielectric zones MFL.

The MFL was designed at 28 GHz and had a radius (R) of 100 mm. This lens was segmented into

Figure 2. Illustration of the HMFL above a ground plane.

10 concentric cylindrical zones, each with a uniform thickness (t) of 10 mm, and placed in an environment of a parallel plate waveguide (PPW). The refractive index for each zone followed the distribution specified in Equation (1). Although the theoretical ϵ_r of the outermost zone is 1, it has been adjusted to 1.19 to satisfy 3D printing requirements. This modification did not compromise the focusing capability of the lens. The selection of 10 concentric zones was done empirically, as increasing the number of layers further did not result in an improved performance according to the full-wave simulation.

Observations indicated that when the HMFL is positioned above a ground plane, it concentrates electromagnetic waves through refraction and reflection, as illustrated in Figure 2. For example, by positioning a source at an angle of incidence $\phi_i = -30^\circ$, image formation occurs at a reflection angle $\phi_r = +30^\circ$. This setup suggests the presence of a virtual source below the ground plane directly opposite the image, where $\phi_i = \phi_r = \phi_v$, and ϕ_v is the virtual source angle.

Alternatively, using a metasurface instead of a ground plane allows manipulating electromagnetic waves at subwavelength scales through a controlled phase and amplitude distribution [21]. This is achieved by designing specific meta-atoms on the surface to produce a tailored refractive index for the electromagnetic waves, allowing precise control of the wavefront passing through the metasurface. As illustrated in Figure 3, placing a source at an incidence angle $\phi_i = -30^\circ$, aligned with the metasurface, facilitated control over the image and thus the virtual source, with a maximum achievable angle of 45° . This angle corresponds to the angle between the source and the image, where $\phi_s = \phi_v$.

The design of a reflective metasurface requires an analysis of electric field phases within the MFL body,

Figure 3. Illustration of the HMFL above a metasurface.

which can be achieved using analytical ray trajectory methods [22]. In this article, a full wave simulation tool, CST Microwave Studio Suite [23] was used to analyse the phases of the electric field within the MFL. To design the reflective metasurface, the MFL, with 12 cuts in the virtual plane throughout its structure, was excited by a linear vertically polarized rectangular horn antenna feed placed at the virtual cut plane 0° at 28 GHz. These virtual cut planes ranged from -90° to $+90^\circ$ at intervals of 15° . All these plane cuts passed through the lens centre, where $R = 100$ mm.

The required phase difference ($\Delta\varphi$) essential to design the subsequent metasurface can be calculated between the electric field phases at two different virtual cut planes corresponding to the focus (φ_s) and the incidence (φ_i) as expressed

$$\Delta\varphi = \varphi_s - \varphi_i \quad (2)$$

For example, when targeting a focus at $\phi_s = +15^\circ$ where the horn antenna is moved at $\phi_i = -30^\circ$, $\Delta\varphi$ between these two virtual cut planes is depicted in Figure 4. It can be seen that $\Delta\varphi$ is equal to 0, and the electric field phases of these virtual cut planes are intersected where $R = 100$ mm. This $\Delta\varphi$ is essential to define the parameters of the phasing elements on the subsequent reflective metasurface.

2.2. Phoenix Unit Cell

In this work, we modified the parameters of the Phoenix unit cell reported in [24] for integration with the proposed HMFL. The Phoenix unit cell consisted of two square loops and a square patch, with dimensions of 5×5 mm. An air gap of 1 mm was introduced between the ground plane and the dielectric substrate to increase the bandwidth [24]. The geometry of the Phoenix unit cell is shown in Figure 5, and its specific attributes are listed in Table 1. A Rogers

Figure 4. Phase difference ($\Delta\varphi$) inside the MFL between the phase of focus (φ_s) and the phase of incidence (φ_i) at 28 GHz.

Figure 5. Geometry of the Phoenix unit cell.

RO3003 material with a thickness of 0.508 mm, ϵ_r of 3 and a loss tangent of 0.001 was used as a substrate. The parameter L_1 was modulated between 0.125 mm and 5.00 mm to obtain the required variations in the phasing element cycle and to meet subsequent fabrication processes. This article considered incident waves propagating through a Floquet waveguide with 10 different dielectric constants ranging from 1.19 to 3.92, corresponding to the dielectric constants of the concentric zones in the MFL. The reflection phases of the Phoenix unit cell considering 5 different dielectric constants are shown in Figure 6.

3. Simulations and discussions

In the simulation setup, a horn antenna feed was designed and used to excite the proposed lenses using CST Microwave Studio Suite [23]. For the MFL, each point on a spherical surface with R is focused on its antipodal point on the same surface. In contrast, the HMFL is noted for producing plane waves that contribute to a highly directive beam [7].

In the basic design, attaching a perfect electric conductor (PEC) to the HMFL is presented. A horn

Table 1. Geometrical parameters of the Phoenix unit cell.

Parameter	Value [mm]
L_1	0.125 – 5.00
L_2	$r \times L_1$
L_3	$r \times L_2$
d_1	$0.06L_1$
d_2	$r \times d_1$
r	0.5
w_x	5
w_y	5

Figure 6. Reflection phase of the Phoenix unit cell within Floquet waveguides with relative dielectric permittivity of 3.92, 3.36, 2.56, 1.80 and 1.22 at 28 GHz.

antenna feed was placed at a $\phi_i = -30^\circ$ angle relative to the lens structure to assess its focusing performance. The focal axis is expected to align at a $\phi_r = +30^\circ$ angle within the architecture of the HMFL beamformer, as illustrated in Figure 7. Observations indicated that energy passes through the 2D reflective HMFL beamformer, interacts with the reflector, and is then directed toward the focal axis. It has been shown that by moving the source around the surface of the reflective HMFL lens of $\pm 30^\circ$, the location of the focal axis can be adjusted to correspond inversely to the incident energy.

Subsequently, a metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer was developed, integrating the HMFL with a 2×40 Phoenix metasurface, as shown in Figure 8. In contrast to the reflective HMFL with a PEC, which generates a focal axis only at the angle opposite to incident energy, this 2D metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer was able to direct the focal axis towards predetermined directions up to a maximum elevation angle of 45° . The performance of this beamformer was examined under both normal

Figure 7. Distribution of the real component of the electric field inside the HMFL with a PEC excited by a horn antenna feed with an oblique incidence of $\phi_i = -30^\circ$ at 28 GHz.

Figure 8. Illustration of the geometry of the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer with a partial front view of the Phoenix metasurface. (Exploded view)

and oblique incidences at angles of $\phi_i = -15^\circ$ and $\phi_i = -30^\circ$.

Initially, the horn antenna feed was used to excite the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer with a normal incidence of 0° to focus at $+15^\circ$ and $+30^\circ$. Subsequently, the source was moved to an oblique incidence of -15° , with the focal axis targeted at 0° and $+30^\circ$. Moving the source further to -30° aligned the focus at 0° and $+15^\circ$.

With an incidence of 0° , an electric field component (E_z) of 1845 V/m at $+16^\circ$ and 1419 V/m at $+32^\circ$ were achieved at 28 GHz, as depicted in Figure 9. Shifts of approximately $+1^\circ$ and $+2^\circ$ were observed for beamforming angles of 15° and 30° , respectively.

Figure 9. Magnitude of E_z for the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer illuminated by a horn antenna feed with a normal incidence of $\phi_i = 0^\circ$ at 28 GHz.

Furthermore, under excitation at 15° , an E_z of 1684 V/m at 0° and 1426 V/m at $+31^\circ$ were achieved, as depicted in Figure 10. Observations showed a precise beamforming angle of 15° and a slight deviation of approximately $+1^\circ$ when aiming for a beamforming angle of 45° . Furthermore, with a source moving to 30° , E_z values were 1477 V/m at -1° and 1361 V/m at $+14.5^\circ$, as shown in Figure 11, with a deviation of approximately -1° observed with beamforming angles of 30° and 45° . The focus axes of these metasurface-augmented beamformers are shown in Figure 12. This figure illustrates the distribution of the real component of the electric field inside the structures of the proposed metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer at 28 GHz considering the three positions of incidence. It shows that energy originating from the source passes through the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer, and is interacted with and manipulated by the metasurface, enabling controlled focal axes in the desired directions.

The proposed metasurface-augmented beamformers demonstrated wideband capabilities within a bandwidth of 22 - 32 GHz. To illustrate the operational bandwidth of the proposed beamformer, Figure 13 shows the distribution of the real component of the electric field inside the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer excited by a horn antenna feed with a normal incidence of 0° to focus at $+15^\circ$ across the frequency band. In addition, Figure 14 shows the maximum E_z achieved in this frequency range. At a separation angle of 15° , the beamformer achieved E_z values exceeding 1500 V/m. Increasing the separation angle to 30° resulted in E_z values above 1230 V/m. At the maximum separation angle of 45° , the values of E_z exceeded 1201 V/m. It was observed that as the beamforming angle increased, the values of E_z decreased since surface waves tend to appear with higher

Figure 10. E_z of the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer illuminated by a horn antenna feed with an oblique incidence of $\phi_i = -15^\circ$ at 28 GHz.

Figure 11. E_z of the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer illuminated by a horn antenna feed with an oblique incidence of $\phi_i = -30^\circ$ at 28 GHz.

sidelobes and losses. Outside this frequency band, the metasurface-augmented beamformer cannot focus.

4. Experimental validation

The prototype of the HMFL beamformer has been manufactured by 3D printing, offering simplicity and cost-effectiveness for laboratory prototypes as well as mass production capability. The construction of the HMFL beamformer used two different materials. In particular, the first six innermost zones measuring 0 mm to 60 mm were printed using a dielectric filament with $\epsilon_{r0} = 4.5$, while the four outermost layers measuring from 60 mm to 100 mm were printed using thermoplastic polylactic acid (PLA) with $\epsilon_{r0} = 2.72$. Two copper planes that serve as PPWs with a thickness

Table 2. The infill percentage values for the 10 dielectric zones of the HMFL.

Layer	ϵ_r	v
1	3.92	83%
2	3.69	76%
3	3.36	67%
4	2.97	56%
5	2.56	44%
6	2.16	33%
7	1.80	46%
8	1.48	27%
9	1.22	12%
10	1.19	11%

of 1 mm were fabricated through a printed circuit board (PCB). The 3D printer used in this research was the Creality Ender 5 S1. The six innermost zones printed on the filament took approximately 26 hours while the four outermost zones printed on the PLA took approximately 4 hours.

To calculate ϵ_r within various zones of the HMFL, the quantity of dielectric material in each segmented zone was modified [25]. Equation 3 was used to determine the required infill volume percentage (v) for achieving a designated ϵ_r based on ϵ_{r0} for filament or PLA, as applicable, in 3D printed dielectric materials [26]. The specific infill percentages across the 10 dielectric zones of the HMFL beamformer are detailed in Table 2.

$$v = \frac{\epsilon_r - 1}{\epsilon_{r0} - 1} \quad (3)$$

The PCB was used to manufacture six metasurfaces, each incorporating 2×40 Phoenix unit cells. The fabrication used commercially available materials, including Roger RO3003 for the substrate, with a thickness of 0.508 mm, and copper for the patches, with a thickness of 0.035 mm. Additionally, a 1 mm thick Rohacell foam was placed beneath the substrate. A copper ground plane was placed beneath the Rohacell foam. The fabricated prototype of the HMFL beamformer and the Phoenix metasurface are shown in Figure 15 and Figure 16, respectively. The setup of the experiment of the 3D printed metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformers was performed using a vector network analyser (VNA) as shown in Figure 17.

In the experimental setup, the measurements of the S-parameter used two horn antennas, which are a Flann standard gain, feature a gain of 15 dBi and an aperture size of 20.60×13.80 mm served as a received antenna, and a horn antenna feed offers a gain of 9 dBi with an aperture size of 14.50×11.00 mm served as a transmitting antenna. We measured normalised E_z in dB along the focal axis, with a total of 21 readings

Figure 12. Distribution of the real component of the electric field inside the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformers excited by a horn antenna feed at 28 GHz: (a) $\phi_i = 0^\circ$ and $\phi_s = +15^\circ$, (b) $\phi_i = 0^\circ$ and $\phi_s = +30^\circ$, (c) $\phi_i = -15^\circ$ and $\phi_s = 0^\circ$, (d) $\phi_i = -15^\circ$ and $\phi_s = +30^\circ$, (e) $\phi_i = -30^\circ$ and $\phi_s = 0^\circ$ and (f) $\phi_i = -30^\circ$ and $\phi_s = +15^\circ$

Figure 13. Distribution of the real component of the electric field inside the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformers excited by a horn antenna feed with a normal incidence of $\phi_i = 0^\circ$ to focus at $\phi_s = +15^\circ$: (a) 22 GHz, (b) 23 GHz, (c) 24 GHz, (d) 25 GHz, (e) 26 GHz, (f) 27 GHz, (g) 28 GHz, (h) 29 GHz, (i) 30 GHz, (j) 31 GHz and (k) 32 GHz.

ranging from $\phi_s - 10^\circ$ to $\phi_s + 10^\circ$. For the setup where the separation angle between the horn antenna feed and the Flann antenna was 15° , the measurement comprised only 15 readings due to their aperture sizes.

Initially, the transmitting horn antenna feed was placed at 0° to evaluate the focusing performance of the 3D-printed HMFL beamformer, with the receiving Flann antenna moved around $+15^\circ$ and $+30^\circ$.

We measured the transmission coefficient $|S_{21}|$ between the two antennas around the focal axis inside the proposed HMFL beamformer. When targeting focus at $+15^\circ$, $|S_{21}|$ measurements were taken from $+10^\circ$ to $+25^\circ$ while an angular spectrum was observed from $+20^\circ$ to $+40^\circ$ when focus was targeted at $+30^\circ$,

as shown in Figure 18 and Figure 19, respectively. Subsequently, with the transmitting horn antenna feed fixed at -15° , the focusing performance was assessed as the receiving Flann antenna was moved around 0° and $+30^\circ$. Similarly, $|S_{21}|$ measurements were taken from -5° to $+10^\circ$ considering the focus at 0° , and from $+20^\circ$ to $+40^\circ$ considering the focus at $+30^\circ$, as shown in Figure 20 and Figure 21, respectively.

Lastly, with the transmitting horn antenna feed fixed at 30° , the focus assessment continued as the receiving Flann antenna was moved around 0° and $+15^\circ$. We measured $|S_{21}|$ from -10° to $+10^\circ$ targeting a focus at 0° , and from $+5^\circ$ to $+25^\circ$ targeting a focus at $+15^\circ$, as shown in Figure 22 and Figure 23,

Figure 14. Maximum E_z of the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer illuminated by a horn antenna feed across the frequency band of 20 - 34 GHz.

Figure 16. Photograph of the fabricated Phoenix metasurface prototype.

Figure 15. Photograph of the fabricated HMFL prototype. The white section was printed using filament, while the black section was printed using PLA.

Figure 17. Photographs of the experimental setup of the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer using the transmitting horn antenna feed and the receiving Flann antenna.

respectively. The maximum measured and simulated E_z of the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer excited with a normal incidence of 0° to focus at $+30^\circ$ and with an oblique incidence of -15° to focus at 0° is shown in Figure 24.

The frame of scanning covers an angular range of 45° around the normal axis. Insert loss of this metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer can be attributed to material selections and feeding network used. This loss can be minimised by using different types of metasurface, improving the feeding networks [27, 28] and using different materials to print the dielectric lens.

The plots show good agreement between the simulated and measured results for the 3D-printed metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformers. For

Figure 18. Measured and simulated E_z of the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer excited by a horn antenna feed with a normal incidence of $\phi_i = 0^\circ$ to focus at $\phi_s = +15^\circ$ at 28 GHz.

Figure 19. Measured and simulated E_z of the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer excited by a horn antenna feed with a normal incidence of $\phi_i = 0^\circ$ to focus at $\phi_s = +30^\circ$ at 28 GHz.

Figure 21. Measured and simulated E_z of the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer excited by a horn antenna feed with an oblique incidence of $\phi_i = -15^\circ$ to focus at $\phi_s = +30^\circ$ at 28 GHz.

Figure 20. Measured and simulated E_z of the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer excited by a horn antenna feed with an oblique incidence of $\phi_i = -15^\circ$ to focus at $\phi_s = 0^\circ$ at 28 GHz.

Figure 22. Measured and simulated E_z of the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer excited by a horn antenna feed with an oblique incidence of $\phi_i = -30^\circ$ to focus at $\phi_s = 0^\circ$ at 28 GHz.

each experimental setup, the shape and trend of the measured data, represented by dashed lines, align with the simulated data, represented by solid lines, particularly near the peak of $|E_z|$. However, minor discrepancies were noticeable at angles away from the peak of $|E_z|$, usually due to material deviation and manufacturing tolerances. In addition, these variations may arise from the use of two different antennas for transmission and reception. In Figure 23, the performance of the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer is shown at the maximum beamforming angle 45° and the maximum source offset position -30° . In these settings, a larger phase change is required for compensation, and manufacturing tolerances have a greater impact, which can potentially

lead to discrepancies. These findings affirm the ability of the beamformer to focus the electric field at the designated angle, making it a suitable candidate for mmWave switching and power division networks.

5. Conclusion

This article presented an innovative 2D metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer, capable of directing its focal axis towards a targeted angle up to 45° . The HMFL beamformer consists of 10 concentric zones and incorporates a reflective metasurface with 2×40 Phoenix unit cells. A horn antenna feed was used to excite this beamformer at normal and oblique incidences of $\phi = -15^\circ$ and $\phi = -30^\circ$. The proposed

Figure 23. Measured and simulated E_z of the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer excited by a horn antenna feed with an oblique incidence of $\phi_i = -30^\circ$ to focus at $\phi_s = +15^\circ$ at 28 GHz.

Figure 24. Maximum measured and simulated E_z of the metasurface-augmented HMFL beamformer excited by a horn antenna feed with a normal incidence of $\phi_i = 0^\circ$ to focus at $\phi_s = +30^\circ$ and with an oblique incidence of $\phi_i = -15^\circ$ to focus at $\phi_s = 0^\circ$ across the frequency band of 22 - 32 GHz. Solid lines represent simulated results, and dashed lines represent measured results.

beamformer operates over a band of 22 - 32 GHz. The beamformer was manufactured using 3D printing technology and subjected to experimental validations. The results confirmed the experimental performance of the beamformer, aligned with the simulations. This metasurface-augmented beamformer can be used for mmWave switching and power division networks.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

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